

What do children think is inside a crab on a seashore in Paraná - Southern Brazil? (Case Study)

Amauri Betini Bartoszeck ^{1,§} and Sue Dale Tunnicliffe ^{2,€}

¹Department of Biology, University of Federal of Paraná, Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil.

²University London Faculty of Education and Society, London, UK.

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Abstract

Children from Southern Brazil have a basic knowledge of internal anatomy of the crab from their everyday life? A total of 434 children 194 aged 5, 67 aged 10 and 173 aged 12 were asked to draw what they think is inside a Brazilian crab which lives in a mangrove swamp. A real preserved seashore crab was presented in the classroom during the class period and children were given 15 minutes to draw the drawing on a A4 sheet of blank paper. These pupils attended 3 public and 1 private schools in an urban area 100 km away from the seashore in Curitiba town. Analysis of the collected drawings by 5 years old pupils revealed that most achieved level 2 "one or more internal organs at random", those at 10 years old achieved level 4 "two or more internal organs in appropriate position, whereas those children 12 years old achieved level 5 mentioning a few organ systems according to the grade level rubric developed by the authors. On the whole very few drawings depicted organ systems. This study intended to evaluate the mental model represented by the drawing which in this case is the expressed model what children think is inside the crab. Invertebrates are a very neglected area in the curriculum of the preschool and first grades of primary school. Internal anatomy investigation of what children think is inside invertebrates is very scarce. This study has shown that children have a poor understanding of the internal organization of organs and organ systems of crabs sometimes pupils depicting human or vertebrate organs (e. g. lung instead of gills, "dog" bones) as a template for explaining their understanding. Heart and brain were the most mentioned organ both genders by all participating ages and respiratory and digestive systems the most mentioned by twelve years old pupils. Educational implications are discussed.

Keywords: crab, invertebrate, drawings, Southern Brazil.

[§]Email: abbartoszeck@gmail.com (Corresponding Author)

[€]Email: s.tunnicliffe@ucl.ac.uk

Resumo

Alunos do sul do Brasil têm um conhecimento básico da anatomia interna do caranguejo. Um total de 434 alunos sendo 194 com 5 anos, 567 com 10 anos e 173 com 12 anos lhes foi pedido para desenharem o que eles acham que se encontra dentro do caranguejo. Um caranguejo fixado em formol foi apresentado durante o período de aula, e os alunos tiveram 15 minutos para fazer o desenho em folha em branco de A4. Esses alunos estão matriculados em três escolas públicas e uma particular em zona urbana há 100 km de distância da praia em Curitiba. A análise dos desenhos coletados dos alunos de 5 anos revelou que a maioria alcançou o nível 2 “um ou mais órgão internos espalhados aleatoriamente”, já aqueles alunos de 10 anos alcançaram nível 4 “dois ou órgãos internos na posição apropriada, ao passo que os alunos de 12 anos alcançaram nível 5, qual seja sobre a rubrica desenvolvida pelos autores. No todo, poucos desenhos apresentação sistema de órgãos bem estabelecidos. Esse estudo teve a intenção de avaliar o modelo mental representado pelos desenhos que no caso é o modelo expresso do que os alunos pensam que está dentro do caranguejo. Os invertebrados são uma área muito negligenciada no currículo da pré-escola e primeiras séries da escola primária. A investigação da anatomia do que os alunos pensam que está dentro dos invertebrados é escassa. Esse estudo mostrou que os alunos tem um parco conhecimento da organização dos órgãos e sistemas de órgãos por exemplo (pulmão em vez de guelras ou brânquias, osso no formato dos vertebrados) como modelo para explicar o seu entendimento. Coração e cérebro foram os órgãos mais mencionados por ambos os sexos em todas as idades e os sistemas respiratório e digestivo os mais mencionados pelos alunos de doze anos. São discutidas implicações educacionais.

Palavras chave: caranguejo, invertebrado, desenhos, sul do Brasil.

1. Introduction

Children notice and find out about living creatures around them. When children deal with living organisms they experience countless opportunities for understanding the natural world around them (Tunnicliffe, 2013; Bartoszeck et al., 2014) [1, 2]. Children are innately interested in living things. A fundamental concept that emerges very early is the sorting of organisms (Greene, 2005) [3]. How to explore, to know about internal structures of living things forms a set of abilities that start with very young children at school as they develop further the first learning experiences of science at school (Keil, 2013) [4].

There is a scarcity of investigations on inner organs and organ systems in invertebrates according to children's ideas (Rybska et al., 2014) [5]; Tunnicliffe, 2015) [6]. Children's picture books about the Brazilian crab just cover daily activities that occur with the invertebrate in the mangrove swamp where the animal lives (Enlourescida, 2008) [7]. The present investigation sought to examine what young

children aged 5, 10 and 12 years old believed asked on their existing understandings. Represent by means of a drawing the internal anatomy of a species of Brazilian crab. A child's drawing as a expressed model is a way children may choose to express her inner mind representation of reality, of information and the experience the child may have from the outside world (Rapp, 2007; [8] Kildan et al., 2013) [9]. In this study, the drawings are products of the drawers imagination kept in his/hers memory (Thompson and Madigan, 2005) [10].

2. Methodology

This study looked at the understanding of pupils aged 5 (N = 194), 10 (N=650 and 12 (N = 171) when representing of the inside anatomy of the crab (*Neohelice granulata* Dana, 1851). An exemplar was taxidermically prepared and shown in the classroom during the class period in 3 public and 1 private urban school in Southern Brazil. Children were given 10-15 minutes to

complete the drawing. Drawings were collected the kindergarten Emilia Ericksen, Rua Xavier da Silva, 504 Curitiba, Paraná, Colégio Estadual Dr. Xavier da Silva, rua Marechal Floriano, 1672, Curitiba, PR e Colégio da Polícia Militar, Rua Almirante Gonçalves, 1957 Curitiba, Paraná and kindergarten Tistu, Rua Alexandre Gutierrez 415, Curitiba, Paraná. All data was collected subjected to full consent of parents and principles of all the educational institutions involved in this study.

Drawings were analyzed by using a rubric scale protocol devised for scoring drawings of internal anatomy adapted for invertebrates describing stages of development of organs and organ systems, Tables (1) and Table (2).

Table 1: Organ and organ system scoring rubric scale for Level (n=1 to 6).

1	No internal recognizable organs.
2	One or more internal organs showed at random.
3	One internal organ (e. g. heart) in appropriate position.
4	Two or more internal organs (stomach, gills) in appropriate position but no extensive relationships indicated between them.
5	One organ system indicated (e. g. gut connecting mouth to anus)
6	Two or three major organ systems indicated (e. g. digestive, circulatory).
7	Four or more organ systems indicated.

Source: (Adapted from Reiss and Tunnicliffe, 2001) [11].

Table 2: Organs belonging to an organ system.

Nervous system	Cerebroid ganglia, supraesophageal ganglion, circumesophageal ganglion, thoracic ganglion, abdominal nerve, optic nerve, nerves;
Digestive system	Cardiac stomach, hepatopancreas, middle (small) intestine, posterior (large) intestine, caecum. , anus;
Circulatory system	Heart, lateral right branch blood vessel, lateral left branch blood vessel
Muscular system	Muscles in the legs and claws,
Excretory system	Bladder, kidney, vas deferens, excretory hole;
Respiratory system	Branchial chambre, gills, openings to the outside;
Reproductive system	Testis, deferens channel, ejaculator channel, penial papillae, ovary branches right and left, spermathecae

Source: (Adapted from Felgenhauer, 1992) [12].

3. Findings

As expected older pupils attained higher grade levels than the younger ones, Tables (3-8).

Table 3: Drawing grade levels achieved by 5 year olds girls.

Source: Authors.

Table 4: Drawing grade levels achieve by 5 year olds boys.

Source: Authors.

Table 4A: Drawings grade levels achieved by 10 year olds girls.

Source: Authors.

Table 5: Drawings grade levels achieved by 10 year olds boys.

Source: Authors.

Table 6: Drawings grade levels achieved by 12 year olds girls.

Source: Authors.

Table 7: Drawings grade levels achieve by 12 year olds boys.

Source: Authors.

The most frequent represented organ on the drawings was the heart and brain and the less

represented were kidney and bladder, Figures (1-3).

Figure 1: Percentage of organs represented in the drawings by 5 year olds (both genders).

Source: Authors.

Figure 2: Percentage of organs represented in the drawings of 10 year olds (both genders).

Source: Authors.

The data revealed the children from nursery or kindergarten up to 4th grade pupils do not make a clear distinction between the biological structures of organ and organ system from thoughts represented as mental images, i. e. pictures of their thoughts as happy memories of vacations, parties and food in restaurants. They progressively draw models trying to explain how an organ or

organ system functions but still have a poor idea of their shapes.

Figure 3: Percentage of organs and organ system represented in the drawings of 12 year olds (both genders).

Source: Authors.

4. Conclusions

Capturing the expressed models, i. e. representations of phenomena placed in the public domain how internal anatomy of invertebrates develop and expand through other educational settings in representative selected areas in Brazil should be a collaborative goal in itself. It is crucial that the practice of “observing with meaning” is taught from the preschool onwards. Although the internal structure information of the crab supplied by this sample of pupils was not accurate they provided their conceptions taking themselves as a template. It is claimed that children are initially able to construct visual representations of their ideas and later achieve a higher level of understanding (Tversky, 2005) [13]. In spite of the fact that Brazilian textbooks for the age range of this study cover only external anatomy pupils are influenced by products of media and visits to science centers. Thus, teachers probing pupils’ thinking in this particular issue is the starting point for more effective teaching in the classroom emphasizing fresh water crab dissection on trays having a colour atlas as a helping guide (Muedra, 1959) [14].

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